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Author(s)	Rogier van der Stijl (UMCG), Maiken Elvestad Gabrielsen (NTNU), Zisis Kozlakidis (IARC/WHO), Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI-ERIC), Nancy Mah (Fraunhofer), Minttu Sauramo (HUS)
Other contributors	Caren Rizk, Faiza Imtiaz, Feride Simsek (School of Public Health, City University of London)
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1. DOCUMENT INFORMATION

1.1 Document history

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1.2 Glossary

<u>Abbreviation / acronym</u>	<u>Description</u>
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
EBRAINS	European Brain Research Infrastructures
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EIRENE	Research Infrastructure for EnvlRonmental Exposure assessment in Europe
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, and Societal Issues
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (guiding principles for data management)
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
RI	Research Infrastructure
WHO	World Health Organization

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the current landscape for strategies engaging participants and incentivizing researchers in research infrastructures (RIs) related to the sharing and using of data. Following a general introduction, the document describes findings from a literature review for the current status of stakeholder engagement of three distinct groups particularly relevant for large medical cohorts: research participants, researchers and cohort managers. The report ultimately contrasts the findings of the literature review with the combined knowledge and experiences of the authors and concludes with recommendations on engagement and incentive practices for research infrastructures.

3. INTRODUCTION

The INTEGRATE LMedC consortium was established to develop a solid concept to guide and support decision-making for the next-generation research infrastructures (RIs) to facilitate efficient utilization and harmonization of large medical cohorts (LMedC) and consequently to accelerate scientific and medical research in Europe and worldwide. Partners include established ESFRI infrastructures such as BBMRI-ERIC, ECRIN, EIRENE, and EBRAINS, as well as additional highly interdisciplinary partners with data management and biobanking expertise. The consortium will take into consideration the users' needs and obstacles for the efficient use of a LMedC RI by performing a gap analysis to identify what is missing from cohort data and samples, RI tools and services, quality measures, and governance models. The consortium will prepare a feasibility study for federated data analysis of LMedC to identify the IT technologies and architecture to ensure appropriate data stewardship and the long-term availability of LMedC. A concept outline, including a governance plan and guiding principles for data access and data protection policies, will be developed to ensure the availability of data and samples from LMedC and their subsequent reuse for research. The project will culminate in an overarching RI concept for the management, integration, and sustainability of LMedC studies, along with a financial and operational plan for the implementation of novel service and access possibilities for the research community.

Medical cohorts play a crucial role in advancing both research and healthcare knowledge by providing valuable insights into disease development, progression, and treatment outcomes. Medical cohorts refer to a (often large) group of individuals with shared characteristics, who may be followed over time, collecting detailed clinical, genomic, phenotypic, lifestyle, and/or environmental/exposure data to better understand the underlying mechanisms of diseases and identify factors that influence health outcomes. By tracking participants' health status and outcomes over extended periods, large medical cohorts (LMedC) enable researchers to uncover associations between various risk factors, biomarkers, and disease outcomes, paving the way for the development of more targeted interventions. Additionally, medical cohorts can serve as powerful platforms for evaluating the effectiveness of healthcare interventions, including new treatments, diagnostic tools, and public health-oriented preventive strategies. Thus, by assessing real-world outcomes within and between diverse populations, medical cohorts provide critical evidence to inform healthcare policies and public health initiatives, ultimately improving health outcomes on a population level.

Within Work Package 3 of INTEGRATE LMedC the following working definition for Large Medical Cohorts was established (D3.1): a medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic of exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. The criteria for considering a medical cohort as “large” are the following:

- A clinical cohort comprising over 1000 participants selected for a health condition; or
- A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or
- A population cohort comprising over 10,000 participants.

Without research participants’ providing their data and samples in the first place and without researchers utilizing the data and samples, LMedCs are dormant repositories at best.

The envisaged European RI for LMedC needs to engage with different stakeholder groups, depending on its final setup, products and services. Main stakeholder groups will likely be cohort participants (individuals of whom biological samples and data are collected), cohort managers (data/sample facilitators) and researchers (data/sample users). As such, engagement and incentive strategies for these groups need to be developed if the intended RI for LMedC is to succeed.

A main topic for the LMedC RI will be to promote the sharing and usage of collected data and samples from existing cohorts. Not having FAIR research data diminishes the return on public money.¹ The current manner of working fails to capitalize on the value of these research outputs. Underutilization of cohorts and biobanks has been a concern for some time.² Bottlenecks on different levels lie at the basis of insufficient sharing and use:³⁻⁶

- Scientific system: e.g. promotion of new instead of validation and reuse of existing infrastructures and collections results in researchers building new cohorts while similar cohorts already exist, subsequently increasing competition between cohorts; Lack of career-related recognition for researchers building a cohort and sharing data.⁷⁻⁹
- Legislative and regulatory: e.g. different laws between countries; different access conditions and review policies per institution and/or cohort
- Cohort: e.g. limited findability and accessibility (FAIR), unclear data access conditions and issuance structures, mismatch in collected data/samples and research requirements
- Resources: e.g. data user groups (researchers) have limited resources to pay for fees associated with access to data and samples; cohort managers have limited time and personnel to share data and samples.
- Quality: e.g. samples and/or (meta-)data are not standardized/harmonized; insufficient documentation impairs sharing and reuse, concerns over data integrity;
- Skills: e.g. lack of research data management literacy,¹⁰ lack of awareness about FAIR and ELSI issues related to data sharing.
- Behavioral: e.g. protectionism of collected samples and data due to the competition between researchers on funding and publishing results; Not-Invented-Here syndrome leading to a

preference to collect own samples and data instead of using a cohort from another institution or country.⁷

While a complete solution to the above bottlenecks is multifactorial, correct and timely stakeholder engagement and incentive strategies will be required to improve sample and data sharing and use. As such, within WP6 “ELSI, FAIR and fairness”, the authors have analysed the current landscape for strategies engaging and incentivising participants (data/sample providers), researchers (data/sample users) and cohort managers (data/sample facilitators) in RIs related to the sharing and using of data. This document describes a literature review (methods described in Appendix A) for the current status of stakeholder engagement and incentives and presents recommendations for future RIs.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 Participant engagement and incentive strategies

4.1.1 Introduction

European RIs have recognized the value of involving patients and the public in the research process, moving beyond traditional, passive roles of receiving research results towards a more (inter)active collaboration (ESFRI Landscape 2024)¹¹. This engagement aims to align research more with the needs and experiences of the public, and in the case of medical/health infrastructures with patient groups, leading to more relevant and impactful outcomes- perhaps also at a faster pace (eg., Patient and Citizen Pillar <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/stakeholder-forum/>). Various initiatives and frameworks have been established to facilitate this collaboration, leveraging the emerging digital environment, enabling patients to contribute to the design, implementation, and dissemination of research.

For example, the European Patients' Academy on Therapeutic Innovation (EUPATI) is a patient-led initiative that empowers patients and advocates with knowledge and skills to actively engage in the research and development of medicines (<https://eupati.eu/>). Specifically, EUPATI has created a Toolbox, i.e., an online platform offering resources and training modules on the clinical research process. Additionally, virtual training courses enable patients to better understand and contribute to study designs, ethical reviews, and dissemination of results. In this way the 'citizen scientists', whether patient or not, are empowered to co-design and evaluate research proposals, and eventually integrating their perspectives into the wider research ecosystem.

Similar initiatives have been funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) scheme, such as IMI PREFER (Patient Preferences in Benefit Risk Assessments; <https://www.imi-prefer.eu/w/ip/>) and IMI PARADIGM (Patients Active in Research and Dialogues for an Improved Generation of Medicines; <https://imi-paradigm.eu/>). The former (IMI PREFER) aims to involve patients in the early stages of research, focusing on integrating patient preferences into benefit-risk assessments. To this end they utilize online surveys, focus groups, webinars, to identify patient-driven priorities. The latter (IMI PARADIGM) aims to foster meaningful patient involvement in medicines research and development, by holding digital patient advisory boards to enable real-time collaboration on trial design and communication strategies. IMI (now Innovative Health Initiative, IHI) schemes are typically public-private collaborations, providing examples for the successful collaboration of diverse stakeholders. Moreover, the patient and wider public involvement in these infrastructures is anticipated to enhance the quality and relevance of research but also creates a driving force to promote transparency, trust, and inclusivity. It is understood that by incorporating the perspectives of patients, research can better address real-world health challenges, resulting in more patient-centred care^{12,13}. However, this engagement can also foster the development of new tools and methodologies that support patient participation, ensuring that their voices are heard and integrated throughout the research process. As a result, patient engagement is increasingly seen as a relevant component of European RIs, complementing the efforts to drive innovation and improve healthcare outcomes¹⁴.

4.1.2 Participant engagement: Literature search results

The literature search focused on the period of the last 15 years, to coincide with the existence of all EU-wide RIs. During this time, participant engagement and incentive strategies in medical cohorts across Europe have increasingly emphasized personalization, digitalization, and sustained interaction to enhance recruitment, retention, and data quality. The identified studies (Appendix B) evidence the growing use of digital tools, such as mobile apps, wearables, and online platforms, to provide participants with real-time feedback, monitor their health, and foster a sense of involvement in research. For example, the Lifelines Cohort Study in the Netherlands^{15,16} utilized personalized digital feedback and regular updates on study progress to maintain high participant retention rates over time. Similarly, the UK Biobank has incorporated participant portals where individuals can access aggregated research findings and track the broader impact of their contributions, thereby reinforcing the sense of personal and collective value.

Incentive strategies have also evolved to include both monetary and non-monetary approaches (the latter more frequent), with a focus on ethical considerations and fairness. Offering some financial compensation for time and effort (e.g., often-mentioned transportation costs), especially in longitudinal studies, can improve participation rates without compromising ethical standards. Non-monetary incentives, such as access to health information, personalized feedback reports, and opportunities to engage with researchers, have proven equally effective in fostering trust and commitment among participants. For instance, the German National Cohort (NAKO)¹⁷ provides participants with detailed health assessments, which serve as a tangible benefit and incentive for continued participation.

Moreover, community-based and culturally tailored engagement strategies have been recognized as critical for recruiting and retaining diverse populations in medical cohorts. Studies like the HELIUS (Healthy Life in an Urban Setting)¹⁸ cohort in Amsterdam have demonstrated the importance of involving community leaders, using multilingual materials, and addressing cultural sensitivities to improve participation among ethnic minorities. Additionally, leveraging social media and online campaigns has emerged as a cost-effective strategy to reach younger and digitally savvy populations, as seen in the Danish Diet, Cancer, and Health Study¹⁹.

4.1.3 Participant engagement: Literature Conclusions

In conclusion, from the literature review it is shown that LMedC will continue to prioritize and leverage emerging digital technologies in an effort to maintain a focus on inclusivity and personalization. To this end, expanding the use of wearable devices, mobile apps, and digital health platforms can provide participants with real-time feedback, health insights, and interactive experiences, which enhance their sense of involvement and contribution to research²⁰⁻²². However, these tools should be designed to be user-friendly, accessible across different age groups, and compatible with varying levels of digital literacy. To this end, there can be a tiered engagement strategy based on the different levels of digital literacy. For example, higher digital literacy can offer advanced engagement tools, such as mobile-enabled apps or even wearables, for real-time data collection. Moderate digital literacy, can enable simplified digital tools (e.g., email newsletters) with offline support (e.g., phone-based support)²³. Very low/no digital literacy would have to prioritize non-digital engagement models;

these can include for example, paper-based or in-person surveys, focus group discussions, and ‘ambassadors’ (for example, trained community health workers or local advocates to help to engage with research participants, who can be patients, nurses, researchers or school teachers). There is considerable variation in patient and public preferences with regards to consent mechanisms, level of control, the type of incentivization and the conditions under which individuals may be willing to engage with data sharing platforms. As such, platforms for participant engagement need to be flexible to meet the diversity of its user’s preferences²⁴.

For digitally literate patients fostering long-term engagement and adherence to study protocols is critical. Using the principles of co-production and collaboration with patients and citizens has proven to have a financial and practical value²⁵. Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) to deliver personalized health recommendations and reminders could further increase effectiveness and tailor messages. For instance, AI-driven personalized communication could inform participants of how their specific contributions are shaping scientific discoveries, thereby increasing motivation and commitment. This concept of reciprocity, incentivised by a reward, is shown to be strongly beneficial both for retention of patients and engagement with the cohort.²⁶

As mentioned by a few publications, inclusivity should remain a central focus in such future strategies to ensure the participation of underrepresented and vulnerable populations. In practice this means that LMedC, and studies thereof, must adopt culturally sensitive and community-tailored approaches by engaging local leaders, offering multilingual resources, and addressing barriers such as transportation, time, and trust.²⁷ Also, the cohort TRAILS²⁸ shows that personal contact with long-term staff members can build trust amongst participants and result in high engagement and retention rates. (personal communication) Financial incentives, if available, should be carefully balanced with non-monetary benefits, such as access to health assessments, opportunities to contribute to study design, and regular updates on research progress. When patients are involved in the research process, the questions being asked are more likely to reflect real-world concerns and priorities allowing to integrate valuable perspectives on what works best in practice. This helps create solutions that are more applicable, accessible, and usable. However, it remains to be further studied how to reach and engage diverse populations including societal and disease specific criteria in a tailored fashion (e.g. rare disease patients, working parents, digital natives).

In order to reach younger, digitally immersed populations, LMedC could make greater use of social media campaigns and gamified engagement techniques. Thus, it is anticipated that by combining technological innovation with equity-focused strategies, LMedC can foster sustained engagement, expand diversity, and enhance the overall impact of their research. Overall, within the European landscape the participant engagement (and retention) is strongly dependent on the effective use of the appropriate (digital or classic but certainly innovative) tools for the targeted population. In practice, however, incentives for patients vary widely and are, more often than not, context-dependent with the absence of any standardization, adequate funding or commonly emerging incentives strategy.

It has to be noted that in the literature review participant engagement at the local cohort level is most frequently reported²⁹- as opposed to participant engagement at the level of RIs, which is rarely reported.³⁰ This is anticipated, as local cohorts have a more direct interest in engaging with their participants to enhance data collection and participant retention for long-term follow-up. For example, a cohort study addressing community-specific health issues, such as environmental exposures or local dietary habits, requires deep engagement with participants to ensure relevance

and inclusivity. This might involve collaboration with local healthcare providers, community leaders, and patient advocacy groups to design and implement studies that resonate with participants' lived experiences. On the other hand, European RIs are far-removed and have an indirect connection with individual participants, but rather direct interaction with patient advocacy groups that engage at the European policy level. For example, if a RI would primarily serve as a data repository or provide analytical services for cohorts, direct participant engagement may be less central, focusing instead on individual cohort managers and researchers as main target groups.

4.2 Researcher engagement and incentive strategies in data and sample use

4.2.1 Introduction

Researcher engagement and incentive strategies driven by RIs in Europe have evolved over the last two decades with the consistent aim to foster collaboration, enhance data and sample utilization, and drive innovation in health research. In this context it should be made clear that researchers may have two roles, one as the data or sample provider, and two, as the data or sample end-user. For clarity, this section focuses on the latter.

One prominent approach throughout the European research landscape is the establishment of centralized platforms, such as the Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (BBMRI-ERIC), which offers researchers indirect access to harmonized and high-quality biological samples and associated clinical data.³¹ Such infrastructures not only aim to streamline data sharing and ensure standardization (for example, as mentioned in INTEGRATE LMedC Deliverable 6.1 “Established Assessment Regime”³²) but also incentivize researchers to re-use existing resources by simplifying the application process and reducing administrative burdens. Access to large-scale data and sample repositories, such as those offered by the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) or ELIXIR, enables researchers to perform multi-cohort, cross-disciplinary analyses, significantly increasing the scope and impact of their work. In the highly competitive research environments, access to the standardized data and samples offered by these RIs can confer a competitive advantage for individual researchers and hereby function as a strong incentive for their interaction. In the case of rare diseases, researchers are incentivized to engage with RIs because these infrastructures provide access to harmonized, high-quality datasets from multiple cohorts and countries, enabling more robust and large-scale studies that would be impossible with isolated data of local rare disease cohorts.^{33,34}

Specifically, incentive strategies of RI often include providing open-access resources, digital tools, and technical support to researchers. For example, the aforementioned RIs (BBMRI-ERIC and ELIXIR) provide bioinformatics platforms, training workshops, and computational resources that facilitate the processing and analysis of complex datasets. Moreover, initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) incentivize researchers to share their findings and collaborate by offering secure and interoperable data-sharing environments. Through these platforms, researchers gain recognition for their contributions, which can enhance their academic visibility and lead to further collaborations and future funding opportunities. Several funders support the researcher participation to RIs indirectly, and sharing of findings, providing a more positive (albeit

of limited weight) reception to grant applicants that have incorporated such behaviours into their research plans.³⁵ Furthermore, many RIs encourage researcher engagement by fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and providing opportunities for co-authorship and funding. For example, the Human Brain Project (HBP) and EU-OPENSOURCE³⁶ promote collaborative consortia that bring together scientists from diverse disciplines to address complex health challenges.

These services reduce barriers to entry, particularly for early-career researchers or institutions with limited resources, thereby democratizing access to cutting-edge research tools. However, open questions remain – Is the level of access sufficient to support the increasing number of researchers requiring access? Are these RIs findable and accessible by all researchers, i.e., are there still any ‘techquity’ blind spots? Can these RIs be supported sufficiently financially for the roles and multiplicity of researcher engagement that is anticipated of them? Funding opportunities linked to the use of shared datasets and samples, such as those provided by Horizon Europe, act as incentives for researchers to engage with these infrastructures. Additionally, the promotion of transparent data access policies and the recognition of data generators through formal citation mechanisms could encourage a culture of data sharing and reciprocity. This approach at a primary level ensures ethical and equitable use of data and samples, and at a secondary level also strengthens the trust and collaboration between researchers and RIs. Thus, the ideal scenario would be for European RIs to align resources, funding, and collaboration incentives as part of their wider researcher engagement strategies. The literature search aimed to identify the strategies that were most effective, and whether a single, best of class strategy was emergent.

4.2.2 Researcher engagement: Literature search results

The manuscripts identified in this section (listed in Appendix B) emphasized the need for data integration, standardization, and collaboration as the foundation for engaging researchers and supporting them in addressing diverse healthcare challenges. Articles on rare diseases highlighted the importance of developing common data models to overcome fragmentation, improve interoperability, and enhance research and patient care. This was driven by the researcher and patient community itself (e.g., by EURORDIS, Rare Diseases Europe), in turn creating an RI that was attractive to the researcher community for ongoing engagement. Similarly, studies on cardiovascular disease, haemophilia gene therapy, and sickle cell disease provided similar examples, emphasizing the role of standardized registries, cross-border collaboration, and equitable access to innovative treatments.³⁷⁻³⁹ Efforts to improve cancer screening and public health surveillance, including monitoring congenital anomalies and waterborne diseases, underlined the critical role of integrated data systems, systematic monitoring, and international partnerships in achieving better health outcomes. Having said that, there were substantially fewer papers identified in our search in terms of incentive strategies for data and samples use by researchers. Any such strategies, if reported, were very narrow in focus and generally time-limited, coinciding with specific research funding cycles. This highlights a major challenge - projects have limited lifetimes. RIs could play a role in taking up their outputs to achieve impact beyond a project's lifetime of the initial research funding.

The identified manuscripts collectively revealed a focus on leveraging shared resources, systematic frameworks, and technological tools to engage with researchers and to address complex health

issues at regional and international levels. The overarching themes included building robust infrastructure for data sharing, fostering multidisciplinary collaboration, and promoting equitable access to healthcare innovations, i.e., in alignment with the Open Science policies of the EU. Moving one step further, the integration of public health strategies with precision medicine and advanced surveillance systems are understood and applauded by the research community, however, the pathway for participating in those is not as well-defined. Finally, it is true to say that the manuscripts demonstrated a holistic approach to tackling both chronic and emerging health challenges, driving improvements in research, care delivery, and policy development through researcher engagement. In other words, the engagement of the researchers was viewed as part of the wider research context. An additional literature search on general data sharing incentives in biomedical research (see appendix B for search method) provided further insights. Incentives for data sharing include providing academic credit, appointment and recognition, such as increased citations and open science badges.^{1,3,40}

The current evaluation of scientific standing and productivity of researchers relies on the number of publications and citations and fails to take into account data generation and sharing. Although co-authorship is often awarded for sharing data and provides a major incentive, this might be in conflict with authorship guidelines that require foremost an intellectual contribution to the proposed article.⁴ Approaches that qualify data generators as *contributors* or *collaborators* –or another designation – instead of authors might provide a direction forward.⁹ This aligns with the CRediT approach which was introduced to standardize contributor/authorship statements.⁴¹ Several new data-related altmetrics have been proposed to credit data generators and sharing, although these have yet to prove themselves by generating sufficient evidence after implementation.⁴ An example are Open Data Badges, which are described as an effective intervention to promote open data practices. These badges provide a visible mark of recognition for researchers who share their data, encouraging transparency and openness in research.⁴² Specific data journals that publish data sets or data sources as citable entities with traceable identifiers are another way to create incentives for sharing. Such a data article provides direct credit for a researcher within the current scientific system, as it adds another publication and provides downstream citations.⁴ For LMedCs this appears similar to publishing a cohort profile or description paper which is then referenced in future studies.

A recurring theme is the need for clear policies and regulations to facilitate data sharing. However, results from the literature show that data sharing and open data policies provide a poor incentive for researchers with regards to data sharing.⁴⁰ An interview study with funding agencies showed that mandates for sharing cohort data are not supported by those agencies due to data protection regulations, legislations and monitoring issues. Also, policy measures that could restrict the decision-making authority of researchers related to data sharing were generally not supported by funding agencies.⁴³ Some experts also question the need for specific policies on incentives, as the research culture is already shifting towards FAIR and Open Science. As a result, the new generation of researchers will likely be used to sharing and collaborating on data, 'solving' the problem over time.⁴⁴

4.2.3 Researcher engagement: Literature Conclusions

From the literature review, it is clear that as career progression is strongly dependent on recognition, this becomes a central tenet in the incentivization strategies. Therefore, initiatives related to the

acknowledgment in publications and formal citation of datasets and biospecimens should be further emphasized to reward data generators and promote a culture of reciprocity.^{9,45} Equally so, these incentives are only valuable to a limited number of researchers and their career paths. Study nurses or medical technical staff, for instance, are not incentivized by article recognition, whereas for others it is the only currency that counts. However, the topic of credit and recognition is clearly a systemic challenge and no clear solution with sufficient evidence has emerged yet. The role of a RI specifically for LMedC will be limited in solving such a systemic issue, although it would be possible to promote or pilot certain approaches. Action is required on a higher and broader scientific policy level together with funders and publishers.

A clear conclusion is the need for consistent and long-term European promotion of FAIR and Open Science. Through policies and funding programmes a cultural shift can be accomplished. By stimulating data standardization, building data infrastructures and promote collaboration between researchers and other stakeholders progress is already made within specific disease domains. The overarching themes included building robust infrastructure for data sharing, fostering multidisciplinary collaboration, and promoting equitable access to healthcare innovations, i.e., in alignment with the Open Science policies of the EU.

4.3 Cohort manager engagement and incentive strategies for data and sample sharing

4.3.1 Introduction

Cohort managers serve as intermediaries between researchers, participants, and RIs, ensuring that ethical and operational frameworks for sharing are upheld. To engage cohort managers, European RIs implemented strategies that highlight the value of collaboration and the recognition of their pivotal role. For example, BBMRI-ERIC and ECRIN (European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network) host dedicated forums, webinars, and workshops tailored for cohort managers to address challenges in data and sample sharing, including standardization, compliance, and logistical coordination. These events provide a platform for cohort managers to share best practices, discuss innovative strategies, and build professional networks, fostering a sense of community and shared purpose.

As most cohort managers are established professionals, incentive strategies often focus on professional development, recognition, and institutional benefits. For example, RIs, such as BBMRI-ERIC, have started to provide specialized training programs and certifications for cohort managers, enabling them to stay updated on emerging technologies, ethical standards, and data management practices. This enhances their professional expertise and empowers them to streamline processes for data and sample sharing within their cohorts. Moreover, recognizing the critical contributions of cohort managers through co-authorship on research publications, acknowledgments in consortium reports, and invitations to participate in high-profile conferences further incentivizes their engagement. For instance, several Horizon Europe-funded projects (e.g., canSERV; <https://www.canserv.eu/>) have integrated cohort manager recognition into their governance models, increasing their visibility and value at both institutional and individual levels.

To further engage cohort managers, RIs increasingly promise to provide tools and resources that will simplify their responsibilities in data and sample sharing. Centralized data-sharing platforms with intuitive interfaces and automated compliance checks aim to reduce the administrative burden on cohort managers, enabling them to focus on strategic and collaborative aspects of their work. One of the most recent examples is the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) that has incorporated cohort management dashboards that allow for real-time tracking of data usage, sample requests, and research outcomes, ensuring transparency and fostering trust.^{46,47} Additionally, incentivizing cohort managers through funding opportunities for infrastructure improvement, such as enhancing biobank capabilities, FAIRification of data or implementing new data collection technologies, aligns their objectives with the broader goals of RIs.

4.3.2 Cohort manager engagement: Literature search results

This search generated the lowest number of identified publications, as cohort managers themselves are not often the focus of research (identified manuscripts are listed in Appendix B). The literature of the last two decades highlights the role of cohort managers as critical stakeholders in bridging the gap between researchers and cohort participants. As mentioned above, European RIs, such as BBMRI-ERIC and ECRIN, introduced tailored workshops, professional development programs, and networking opportunities. Additionally, cohort managers are often involved in the early stages of study design, ensuring that data-sharing policies and participant management strategies are aligned with ethical and operational best practices, as in the case of the Euroheart registry.⁴⁸ This is particularly important, due to the need to integrate increasingly more complex datasets from different data origins, e.g., clinical, biochemical data and data from wearable devices for the same cohorts.

In other examples, incentive strategies for cohort managers have focused on both individual and institutional benefits, as noted in studies of large cohorts: the UK Biobank, the Lifelines Cohort, and the German National Cohort (NAKO). Professional recognition is a key motivator, with cohort managers increasingly acknowledged as co-authors on research publications or collaborators in grant applications. Financial incentives, such as dedicated funding for biobank maintenance or technological upgrades, also serve as institutional motivators, empowering cohort managers to support long-term cohort sustainability. The literature also underscores the importance of creating a community of practice among cohort managers to share best practices, address common challenges, and foster peer support. The BBMRI-ERIC Stakeholder Forum and the ECRIN Roadmap are two such examples, facilitating regular interaction and knowledge exchange between cohort managers across Europe, or the national thematic organizations (e.g., German, Belgian, Polish, French, etc., Biobank Networks).⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ These forums help create a shared sense of purpose and encourage engagement by showcasing the broader impact of their work on advancing scientific research and public health outcomes.

4.3.3 Cohort manager engagement: Literature conclusions

In conclusion, for RIs it is crucial to invest in actions, infrastructure and streamlined processes that support the cohort managers' work. For example, prioritize the development of integrated, user-

friendly platforms that automate administrative tasks, such as tracking sample requests, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and generating usage reports.⁵² This would allow cohort managers to focus more on fostering collaborations and improving cohort quality. Moreover, providing access to data visualization tools and real-time dashboards can empower cohort managers to better communicate the value and impact of their data and samples to both researchers and stakeholders, in particular funding bodies.⁵³ Dedicated funding for technological upgrades, such as enhanced biobank capabilities or secure cloud storage for large-scale data, should be made readily available to ensure cohort managers have the resources needed to manage growing research demands effectively.

Fostering professional development and building a strong recognition system are key to sustaining cohort manager engagement. Expanding opportunities for cohort managers to participate in training programs, certification courses, and leadership workshops can enhance their expertise and elevate their professional profiles.⁵⁴ The creation of leadership and management workshops are encouraged, as most managers have found themselves in the role of cohort manager as a continuation of project management requirements, without targeted training.⁵⁵ To this end, recognition mechanisms should go beyond traditional acknowledgments, offering pathways for cohort managers to be co-authors on publications, invited speakers at conferences, and key collaborators in grant-funded research projects. Establishing a more structured, EU-wide professional network or community of practice specifically for cohort managers (through an ESFRI initiative?) could facilitate peer-to-peer learning, mentorship, and the sharing of innovative practices. Finally, aligning institutional incentives with the personal motivations of cohort managers—such as providing access to funding for capacity building or career advancement—will support long-term commitment and engagement.

5. DISCUSSION

Reflecting on the literature review we conclude that limited papers have actually studied the effectiveness of specific engagement or incentive strategies for specific target groups in the context of RI. Most papers describe use cases or promote certain approaches without a studied effect. Although these papers are helpful to draft potential direction it remains difficult to pinpoint effective strategies. This is further complicated as such strategies are context-dependent; the desired approach will depend on the scope, activities and services of the intended RI for LMedC.

The literature review does demonstrate that the future of healthcare RIs depends on achieving a balance between services, innovation and inclusivity. As precision medicine, supported by integrated genomic, clinical, and environmental data, shows increasingly its potential to revolutionize disease management and prevention in the future, questions relating to the access of and engagement with RIs become important. Whereas the technology to access and combine various datasets is already available, the legal and ethical frameworks for it are not. The GDPR, for instance, provides a comprehensive framework with global reach, but has challenged research organizations, universities and research infrastructures to strike a good balance between enabling research and protecting against liability. Consequently, international regulatory and ethical frameworks and transnational data platforms need to continue evolving to facilitate wider, responsible data sharing across borders.

The largest body of literature search results was available on participant engagement in the context

of research projects or cohorts and biobanks. Although relevant for individual cohorts to pick the right engagement strategy for inclusion and retention, it is questionable if these approaches can be transferred to the level of a RI for LMedC. Most likely such an RI will not include participants itself, as these interactions are at the level of the individual cohort. However, if policy-related and strategic topics are within scope of the RI, interaction and alignment with participant and patient representatives will be required, as for example done within the BBMRI-ERIC Stakeholder Forum. Also, if the LMedC RI will be involved in the design and/or management of multinational or European cohorts then participant engagement approaches similar to IMI/IHI could become relevant. An overarching RI could also play a role in realizing a proportional representation of different populations and underrepresented groups.

Incentive strategies for researchers.

Limited data sharing by researchers is a complex challenge without clear solutions so far. The intended RI on LMedC can play a role in providing relevant technical infrastructure, policy development or specific pilots and projects to promote and enable data sharing. However, most challenges related to data sharing should be addressed on a higher level than a single European RI. An example is the need for sound and widely supported credit and recognition strategies to incentivize data sharing by researchers. Several policy directions have been proposed, but coordinated efforts and overarching policy decisions remain absent so far.

During the last years a cultural shift has been started towards FAIR data and Open Science. This movement will mostly affect the new generation of researchers who start their careers within this new paradigm. Promoting the adoption of the new culture in existing running systems, awareness and rewarding this new way of working will remain relevant in the coming years. This fits well with the need for skill-related capacity-building programs, such as targeted training sessions, mentorship for early-career researchers and workshops on advanced analytics and federated approaches. Such programmes can enhance researcher capabilities and create a pipeline of skilled users on data sharing and data collaboration. This already exists in the more mature RIs and should be anticipated to expand for other more recently established RIs.

Additionally, RIs should leverage more IMI/IHI-style funding tools, to expand funding opportunities linked to the innovative use of shared samples and data, while fostering the classical multi-disciplinary collaborations through calls for joint research proposals. Beyond the user perspective, researchers are also the producers of the data. Indirectly, the strengthening of partnerships with industry and policymakers can co-create research goals and fund infrastructure sustainability, in turn ensuring that these resources remain relevant, accessible, and impactful for researchers.

Several European RIs and LMedC have begun to provide synthetic data to researchers to enhance accessibility while safeguarding privacy and promoting engagement. For example, the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) offers synthetic datasets to allow researchers to test analysis pipelines and explore data structures without compromising sensitive genetic information. Similarly, the UK Biobank and Lifelines have introduced synthetic data initiatives to enable broader use of their resources while maintaining participant confidentiality. Additionally, projects like ELIXIR and its FAIR Data approach promote the generation and sharing of synthetic data to facilitate cross-border collaboration and compliance with data protection regulations. The latter initiative remains in its early stages; however, it is likely that such approaches will multiply across Europe and include a number of larger cohorts. This development seems positive for researcher engagement as it will allow easier

access to data, lowering the threshold for applying to the real data.

The literature on engagement and incentive strategies for cohort managers was limited. It is important to keep in mind that cohort managers are a heterogeneous group, just as LMedC. As a RI it is relevant to distinguish between different cohort manager groups, as they have different needs and require different incentives. Population-LMedC tend to be large cohorts with dedicated cohort managers and sometimes even a separate organization (UK Biobank, Lifelines). Many clinical LMedC have cohort managers who are researchers themselves. This is especially the case for cohort managers of LMedCs which are embedded in a research institution (e.g. university, medical center). In such cases the cohort manager is often also one of the main users of the cohort. This can provide conflicting interests, for example related to data sharing and use. A cohort manager's task is to aim for broad use of the data, as this is the LMedCs *raison d'être*. However, as researcher, the cohort manager might be susceptible to protectionism to get a competitive edge. In addition, embedded LMedCs might not have the resources and tools for large scale participant and researcher engagement, as they depend on the driving force of the principal investigator whose focus is split between the cohort, research, education and/or providing care. Data sharing often comes second place as it requires active attention, time and resources. In addition, several papers discuss the need for RI to establish platforms for data sharing, analysis and the automation of administrative tasks, and build integrated dashboards to track data access and use. In contrast to the conclusions in the literature review, that anticipate a wide adoption of produced tools, the actual information gathered through personal communication points towards a modest level of adoption at best. Given the practical context most LMedC face, we doubt that the establishing of additional platforms and tools is a feasible approach for incentivizing researchers and cohort managers. Most cohort managers rely on and are bound to the software solutions provided by their hosting institute and thus are unable to easily switch to tools provided by European RI. As most institutes hosting LMedC are risk averse, especially when it comes to privacy sensitive patient data, they focus on keeping control limiting the acceptance of software and tooling hosted by a European RI.

Thus, therein lies an inherent point of friction, as RIs will continue to build centralized platforms for samples and data, and to this end they should prioritize developing user-friendly, interoperable entry points that facilitate seamless access to data and biospecimens. In order to support this centralized view of RIs within the EU, it means that the centralized, harmonized repositories should continue to adopt advanced digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), to maintain their competitive advantages (attractive to researchers), enhance data discoverability, streamline analytics, and allow researchers to derive actionable insights more efficiently – and that they should be incentivized in doing so. Additionally, simplifying data access procedures through standardized application processes across different RIs, transparent governance structures, and reduced administrative hurdles would greatly encourage broader participation. Establishing real-time dashboards or interactive tools where researchers can preview available datasets and their characteristics before submission could also improve engagement and reduce unnecessary application rejections.

Data and sample governance is indeed a sensitive and critical topic, especially when it comes to the interaction of cohort managers and RIs. The governance of LMedC requires that for data exchange, clear policies and frameworks to ensure ethical and responsible data access are in place. Typically, the cohort itself retains authority over data access, as it is responsible for safeguarding participant rights and ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines. Thus, decisions on who gets access to the

data often depends on the agreements between the cohort managers and data users. However, when LMedC becomes part of a broader RI, governance may shift to a shared decision-making model or be delegated to the RI entirely. While delegating major governance decisions from individual LMedCs to an overarching European RI might seem positive with regards to potentially increasing data use and sharing, it creates additional difficulties that, when not done with care, might have the opposite effect and lead to a decrease in access and sharing due to distrust and unaccepted practices. Cohort managers may feel a loss of control and autonomy if the RI assumes control over data access, potentially causing concerns about alignment with the cohort's original goals. It may also undermine the motivation of cohort managers. Their investment in time and effort to establish the cohort has been high, leading to a sense of entitlement and resistance towards relinquishing control to an abstract RI entity. Cohort managers may struggle with reconciling RI decisions with ethical commitments to participants, particularly if those decisions prioritize broader research goals over individual concerns. In addition, change of procedure and access needs to be communicated and (if divergent from the original agreement with participants) potentially renegotiated with participants, who may worry about their data being used in ways they did not explicitly consent to, leading to trust issues and fearing potential misuse. How do we maintain and ensure oversight and integrity of such transferred data in the (long-term) future, even after the death of participants? How do we solve liability issues when delegating access control entirely? Also, a RI often lacks the domain specific knowledge and context with regards to the original data collection to correctly interpret and share a collection with new users. This is further hampered by the increasing complexity and size of datasets and different data types to be combined. Despite these shortcomings, involving an RI in the governance might provide the necessary sustainability for valuable data and sample collections which might otherwise be inaccessible to research and its results unavailable to society at large.

Ultimately, the solutions lie in fostering interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder collaboration and by leveraging technological advancements to create a more equitable and efficient global healthcare system. By prioritizing data standardization, ethical governance, and inclusive innovation – including the continuous engagement with patients, patient organizations and the wider public – the healthcare community can ensure that progress and its related information benefits everyone and is accessible to all. This requires acceptance of the governance model chosen and the appropriate financial, technical and expert resources to plan, implement and operate. If done properly, these RI efforts will not only help improve future research and healthcare delivery but also lay the foundation for a more connected and resilient healthcare infrastructure ecosystem in the future and ensure an appropriate interface to the EHDS and the national Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs). Many RIs have decades long experience dealing with sensitive data and/or sample management from both the technical as well as ethical point of view. Equally, data collected outside of EHDS need to be made interoperable and the challenges described for cohort managers are similar to those that will occur when implementing EHDS.

6. LESSONS LEARNT – RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the literature review and the views of the authors we make the following recommendations regarding strategies for engaging and incentivising participants (data/sample providers), researchers

(data/sample users) and cohort managers (data/sample facilitators) for data and sample sharing. These recommendations are not shown in any particular order of priority, the relative prioritization would be context-driven each time.

- Gain clarity on the audience of engagement strategies (citizens, researchers, cohort managers, etc) – tailor the message to the audience you want to reach. As such, do not assume what these stakeholders want or need: engage with them and be prepared for a continuous dialogue, as needs are context-driven and may change over time. This approach needs an appropriate allocation of resources for effective information sharing, including communication plans and their execution.
- Enable trust in the RIs through solid and transparent governance and well-established roles, responsibilities and scope. This will help in the engagement of each stakeholder group.
- Enable the recognition of data generators and data sharers by innovations in the scientific crediting mechanisms. Such formal mechanisms would allow for career progression pathways and hereby incentivise sharing of cohort data. An RI for LMedC could contribute for example by hosting a journal exclusively for cohort profiles (e.g. descriptive papers) and implementing new data sharing metrics together with other RIs, funders, publishers and other relevant stakeholders. Also explore the recognition of non-scientific contributors by innovations in the crediting mechanisms beyond authorship recognition.
- Incentivise the use of LMedC and RIs by researchers through the existing funding mechanisms. Funding calls that require the use of existing data and samples stimulate a cycle of reuse of cohorts. Also, funders should evaluate new cohort initiatives against the existing European cohort landscape.
- Stimulate the creation of synthetic datasets for large medical cohorts, such that data can be shared more easily to facilitate research pilots, without compromising the integrity of the cohort data and the privacy of participants.
- Invest in shared digital infrastructure, for example for storage and archiving of large datasets. This is not only relevant for cohorts but for the European Research Area in general. Low-cost storage and archiving solutions would increase sustainability of LMedC and reduce dependency on non-European service providers.
- Continue investments in training professional staff and researchers to drive skill development and awareness on topics related to data sharing such as FAIR, ethical and legal issues and data management literacy. Training and the related peer-to-peer networks are a way to stimulate engagement of researchers and cohort managers.
- Continue standardization and harmonization efforts on data and samples, on regulatory topics and access and sharing conditions.
- Allow for the co-production of research with patients, citizens, policy makers and researchers by studying, acknowledging and integrating their combined interests and needs.

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8. DISCLAIMER

Where authors are identified as personnel of the International Agency for Research on Cancer/WHO, the authors alone are responsible for the views expressed in this article and they do not necessarily represent the decisions, policy or views of the International Agency for Research on Cancer/WHO.

9. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Devriendt, Thijs, et al. "An agenda-setting paper on data sharing platforms: euCanSHare workshop." *Open Research Europe* 1 (2021).
2. Henderson, Marianne K., Kirstin Goldring, and Daniel Simeon-Dubach. "Advancing professionalization of biobank business operations: Performance and utilization." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 17.3 (2019): 213-218.
3. Perrier, Laure, Erik Blondal, and Heather MacDonald. "The views, perspectives, and experiences of academic researchers with data sharing and reuse: A meta-synthesis." *PloS one* 15.2 (2020): e0229182.
4. Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Data sharing in biomedical sciences: a systematic review of incentives." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 19.3 (2021): 219-227.
5. van der Stijl, Rogier, Peggy Manders, and Elisabeth WHM Eijdem. "Recommendations for a Dutch sustainable biobanking environment." *Biopreservation and biobanking* 19.3 (2021): 228-240.
6. van der Stijl R, Scheerder B, Eijdem L. *BBMRI.nl Workshop: Sustainable sample/data infrastructures. Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure, The Netherlands; 2018. Available at: https://www.bbmri.nl/sites/bbmri/files/Workshop%20Report%20BBMRI-NL_Sustainable%20Sample%20%26%20Data%20Infrastructures.pdf, Last accessed December 22, 2020.*
7. Antons, David, and Frank T. Piller. "Opening the black box of "not invented here": Attitudes, decision biases, and behavioral consequences." *Academy of Management perspectives* 29.2 (2015): 193-217.
8. Perrier, Laure, Erik Blondal, and Heather MacDonald. "The views, perspectives, and experiences of academic researchers with data sharing and reuse: A meta-synthesis." *PloS one* 15.2 (2020): e0229182.
9. Devriendt, Thijs, Pascal Borry, and Mahsa Shabani. "Credit and recognition for contributions to data-sharing platforms among cohort holders and platform developers in Europe: interview study." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 24.1 (2022): e25983.
10. Klingner, Carsten M., et al. "Research Data Management and Data Sharing for Reproducible Research—Results of a Community Survey of the German National Research Data Infrastructure Initiative Neuroscience." *eneuro* 10.2 (2023).
11. European Union, European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Landscape Analysis 2024 (2024). Available at: <https://landscape2024.esfri.eu>, Last accessed 09 January 2025.
12. Snyder, Claire F., et al. "Patient-reported outcomes (PROs): putting the patient perspective in patient-centered outcomes research." *Medical care* 51 (2013): S73-S79.
13. Hoddinott, Pat, et al. "How to incorporate patient and public perspectives into the design and conduct of research." *F1000Research* 7 (2018).

14. European Commission, European data strategy (2023). Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en#:~:text=The%20European%20data%20strategy%20aims,businesses%2C%20researchers%20and%20public%20administrations. Last accessed 09 January 2025.
15. van der Ende, M. Yldau, et al. "The LifeLines Cohort Study: prevalence and treatment of cardiovascular disease and risk factors." *International journal of cardiology* 228 (2017): 495-500.
16. Sijtsma, Anna, et al. "Cohort Profile Update: Lifelines, a three-generation cohort study and biobank." *International journal of epidemiology* 51.5 (2022): e295-e302.
17. Peters, Annette, et al. "Framework and baseline examination of the German National Cohort (NAKO)." *European journal of epidemiology* 37.10 (2022): 1107-1124.
18. Snijder, Marieke B., et al. "Cohort profile: the healthy life in an urban setting (HELIUS) study in Amsterdam, the Netherlands." *BMJ open* 7.12 (2017): e017873.
19. Bondonno, Catherine P., et al. "Vegetable nitrate intake, blood pressure and incident cardiovascular disease: Danish Diet, Cancer, and Health Study." *European Journal of Epidemiology* 36.8 (2021): 813-825.
20. Fortunato, Fernanda, et al. "Digital health and Clinical Patient Management System (CPMS) platform utility for data sharing of neuromuscular patients: the Italian EURO-NMD experience." *Orphanet journal of rare diseases* 18.1 (2023): 196.
21. Rogan, Emma. "Activities of the European multiple sclerosis platform." *European Neurology* 72.Suppl. 1 (2014): 43-46.
22. Rodríguez-Gómez, Octavio, et al. "The MOPEAD project: advancing patient engagement for the detection of "hidden" undiagnosed cases of Alzheimer's disease in the community." *Alzheimer's & Dementia* 15.6 (2019): 828-839.
23. Lucas, Patricia J., Debra Allnock, and Tricia Jessiman. "How are European birth-cohort studies engaging and consulting with young cohort members?." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 13 (2013): 1-9.
24. Hermansen, Anna, Dean A. Regier, and Samantha Pollard. "Developing data sharing models for health research with real-world data: a scoping review of patient and public preferences." *Journal of Medical Systems* 46.12 (2022): 86.
25. Price, Amy, et al. "Patient and public involvement in research: a journey to co-production." *Patient education and counseling* 105.4 (2022): 1041-1047.
26. Henderson, Marion, et al. "Retaining young people in a longitudinal sexual health survey: a trial of strategies to maintain participation." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 10 (2010): 1-11.
27. Tanay, Mary Anne, et al. "Patient and public involvement in research: Reflections and experiences of doctoral cancer nurse researchers in Europe." *European Journal of Oncology Nursing* 64 (2023): 102351.

28. Oldehinkel, Albertine J., et al. "Cohort profile update: the tracking adolescents' individual lives survey (TRAILS)." *International journal of epidemiology* 44.1 (2015): 76-76n.
29. Paglialonga, Alessia, et al. "eHealth for patients with rare diseases: the eHealth Working Group of the European Reference Network on Rare Multisystemic Vascular Diseases (VASCERN)." *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 16 (2021): 1-12.
30. Psyrris, A., et al. "Strategies to promote translational research within the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) Head and Neck Cancer Group: a report from the Translational Research Subcommittee." *Annals of oncology* 21.10 (2010): 1952-1960.
31. Holub, Petr, et al. "BBMRI-ERIC directory: 515 biobanks with over 60 million biological samples." *Biopreservation and biobanking* 14.6 (2016): 559-562.
32. Mah, N., Michaela Th., M., Kozlakidis, Z., & Jongerius, J. (2024). INTEGRATE LMedC: D6.1 Established Assessment Regime (1.0). Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14176680>. Last accessed 09 January 2025.
33. Ali, S. R., et al. "Supporting international networks through platforms for standardised data collection—the European Registries for Rare Endocrine Conditions (EuRRECa) model." *Endocrine* 71 (2021): 555-560.
34. Viviani, Laura, et al. "The European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry: valuable lessons learned on how to sustain a disease registry." *Orphanet journal of rare diseases* 9 (2014): 1-14.
35. European Commission. Horizon Europe. Work Programme 2023 – 2025; 3. Research Infrastructures (European Commission Decision C(2024) 2371 of 17 April 2024), Section 'Specific features for Research Infrastructure. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-3-research-infrastructures_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf, Last accessed January 30, 2025.
36. Brennecke, Philip, et al. "EU-OPENSREEN: a novel collaborative approach to facilitate chemical biology." *SLAS DISCOVERY: Advancing Life Sciences R&D* 24.3 (2019): 398-413.
37. Bernts, Lucas HP, et al. "Position statement on access to care in rare liver diseases: advancements of the European reference network (ERN) RARE-LIVER." *Orphanet journal of rare diseases* 14 (2019): 1-8.
38. Orbach, Daniel, et al. "The European Paediatric Rare Tumours Network-European Registry (PARTNER) project for very rare tumors in children." *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 68 (2021): e29072.
39. Reiss, Ulrike M., et al. "Haemophilia gene therapy—Update on new country initiatives." *Haemophilia* 28 (2022): 61-67.
40. Woods, Helen Buckley, and Stephen Pinfield. "Incentivising research data sharing: a scoping review." *Wellcome open research* 6 (2022): 355.
41. Brand, Amy, et al. "Beyond authorship: Attribution, contribution, collaboration, and credit." *Learned Publishing* 28.2 (2015).

42. Rowhani-Farid, Anisa, Adrian Aldcroft, and Adrian G. Barnett. "Did awarding badges increase data sharing in BMJ Open? A randomized controlled trial." *Royal Society open science* 7.3 (2020): 191818.
43. Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Policies to regulate data sharing of cohorts via data infrastructures: An interview study with funding agencies." *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 168 (2022): 104900.
44. Guerrini, Christi J., et al. "Fresh takes on five health data sharing domains: Quality, privacy, equity, incentives, and sustainability." *Frontiers in big Data* 6 (2023): 1095119.
45. Hood, Amelia SC, and William J. Sutherland. "The data-index: An author-level metric that values impactful data and incentivizes data sharing." *Ecology and Evolution* 11.21 (2021): 14344-14350.
46. Baglioni, Miriam, et al. "The OpenAIRE research community dashboard: on blending scientific workflows and scientific publishing." *Digital Libraries for Open Knowledge: 23rd International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPDL 2019, Oslo, Norway, September 9-12, 2019, Proceedings* 23. Springer International Publishing, 2019.
47. Aritzi, Anastasia, Ioanna Grypari and Leonidas Pispiringas. "OpenAIRE Monitor Institutional Dashboard: Our new service tailored to your needs". OpenAIRE. Available at: <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-monitor-institutional-dashboard-our-new-service-tailored-to-your-needs>, Last accessed January 30, 2025.
48. Wallentin, Lars, et al. "Euroheart: European Unified Registries On Heart care Evaluation and Randomized Trials: an ESC project to develop a new IT registry system which will encompass multiple features of cardiovascular medicine." (2019): 2745-2749.
49. Klingler, Corinna, et al. "Evaluating the German Biobank node as coordinating institution of the German Biobank alliance: engaging with stakeholders via survey research." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 18.2 (2020): 64-72.
50. Witoń, Małgorzata, et al. "Organization of BBMRI. pl: the Polish biobanking network." *Biopreservation and biobanking* 15.3 (2017): 264-269.
51. Linsen, Loes, et al. "Biobank quality management in the BBMRI. be network." *Frontiers in medicine* 6 (2019): 141.
52. Hogan Smith, Kay. "Review of rare diseases resources: national organization for rare disorders (nord) rare disease database, nih genetic and rare diseases information center, and orphanet." *Journal of Consumer Health on the Internet* 21.2 (2017): 216-225.
53. Haven, Tamarinde L., Martin R. Holst, and Daniel Strech. "Stakeholders' views on an institutional dashboard with metrics for responsible research." *Plos one* 17.6 (2022): e0269492.
54. Lawrence, Philip, et al. "Ten years of experience in training Biobank managers at master's level in France." *Biobanking of Human Biospecimens: Lessons from 25 Years of Biobanking Experience* (2021): 135-151.
55. Sinner, Philip, and Dimitri Prandner. "Let Others Shine: Key Competencies in European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities." *8th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'22)*. Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València, 2022.

56. Pausan, M., Schlünder, I., & Mayrhofer, M. T. (2024). Information Points for Citizens under the EHDS Workshop Report V2.0. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14196766>, Last accessed January 30, 2025.

APPENDIX

A.1. Search string and keywords used in literature search

A systematic search was conducted across three academic databases—MEDLINE, Scopus, and Ovid—to identify relevant studies. The search strategy employed predefined keywords encompassing themes related to patient management, administrative personnel, data utilization, and medical cohorts. The search was limited geographically to Europe and publications in English. Case studies, posters, editorials, letters to the editor, communication and conference reports were excluded.

The literature search yielded 96 papers in total, 54 from MEDLINE, 40 papers from Scopus, and 2 papers from Ovid after duplicate removal. The remaining studies were screened for relevance to the research objectives and were all considered relevant for inclusion. The search string is shown below and keywords used in the literature search in the last table.

Search string for patient engagement.

- 1 patient engagement/ (37137)
- 2 (patient* adj3 (engag* or motivat* or enrol* or interaction or collaborat*)).ab. (818236)
- 3 1 or 2 (849623)
- 4 administrative personnel/ or hospital administrator/ or medical director/ (82904)
- 5 manager/ (61486)
- 6 (managers or supervisors or directors or administrators).ab. (380116)
- 7 4 or 5 or 6 (462279)
- 8 access to information/ (41322)
- 9 (data adj3 (sharing or issuance or access* or exchang* or governance or discovery)).ab. (99058)
- 10 8 or 9 (138575)
- 11 cohort or medical research infrastructure/ (1721023)
- 12 europe population register/ (0)
- 13 (cohort or register or data bank or data set or data collection).ab. (4009547)
- 14 11 or 12 or 13 (4564603)
- 15 3 and 7 and 10 and 14 (96)

Search string for researcher engagement.

As above, replace 1 with “researcher engagement”, and remove step 2 completely.

Search string for manager engagement.

As above, replace 1 with “manager engagement”, and remove step 2 completely.

A.2. Search string and keywords used in additional literature search

The first literature search (A.1) was supplemented with an additional search in PubMed with a broader search string and without the specific target groups (participant, cohort user, cohort manager). The goal was to identify additional recent papers on data sharing incentives in general. The search was limited to publications in English and the time period 2020-2025. Case studies, posters, editorials, letters to the editor, communication and conference reports were excluded. The

literature search yielded 135 papers. The papers were screened on title resulting in 19 papers relevant for inclusion (see Appendix B.2. for list). The search string used was:

(incentiv*[Title/Abstract]) AND (data sharing[Title/Abstract]) - Search Results - PubMed

Search words	engagement and incentive strategies	cohort managers (data/sample facilitator)	sharing data	Cohorts and research infrastructures
relevant keywords	engagement incentive motivation participation involvement interaction collaboration cooperation strategy	data provider manager facilitator coordinator steward administrator supervisor? director?	data issuance data sharing data use data usage issuance sharing FAIR data exchange collaboration data accessibility data re-use data governance data discovery sample (in combination with the above) biological sample biosample biospecimen secondary use	cohort registry databank database biobank biorepository longitudinal cohort study longitudinal study clinical cohort population cohort collection databank collection biobank collection data collection medical cohort data infrastructure research infrastructure rare disease cohort patient registry patient cohorts dataset big data Biological Specimen Bank biobanking stem cell bank brain bank tissue bank

relevant MeSH terms

Cohort Studies[Mesh]
Data Collection[Mesh]
Datasets as Topic[Mesh]
Big Data[Mesh]
Records [MESH]
Registries [MESH]
Databases, Factual[Mesh]
Biological Specimen Banks[Mesh]

B.1. List of references from literature search

Participant engagement and incentive strategies

1. Fortunato F et al. (2023) 'Digital health and Clinical Patient Management System (CPMS) platform utility for data sharing of neuromuscular patients: the Italian EURO-NMD experience', *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 18(1), p. 196.
2. Casareto, L. et al. (2024) 'ERN BOND: The key European network leveraging diagnosis, research, and treatment for rare bone conditions', *European journal of medical genetics*, 68, p. 104916.
3. Avitzur, Y., Pahl, E. and Venick, R. (2024) 'The Development of the International Intestinal Failure Registry and an Overview of its Results', *European journal of pediatric surgery : official journal of Austrian Association of Pediatric Surgery ... [et al] = Zeitschrift fur Kinderchirurgie*, 34(2), pp. 172–181.
4. Joneborg, U. et al. (2023) 'European multidisciplinary tumor boards support cross-border networking and increase treatment options for patients with rare gynecological tumors', *International journal of gynecological cancer : official journal of the International Gynecological Cancer Society*, 33(10), pp. 1621–1626.
5. Reiss UM et al. (2022) 'Haemophilia gene therapy-Update on new country initiatives', *Haemophilia : the official journal of the World Federation of Hemophilia*, 28 Suppl 4, pp. 61–67.
6. Ammour, N. et al. (2023) 'TransFAIR study: a European multicentre experimental comparison of EHR2EDC technology to the usual manual method for eCRF data collection', *BMJ health & care informatics*, 30(1).
7. Tanay, M.A. et al. (2023) 'Patient and public involvement in research: Reflections and experiences of doctoral cancer nurse researchers in Europe', *European journal of oncology nursing : the official journal of European Oncology Nursing Society*, 64, p. 102351.
8. Orbach D et al. (2021) 'The European Paediatric Rare Tumours Network - European Registry (PARTNER) project for very rare tumors in children', *Pediatric blood & cancer*, 68 Suppl 4, p. e29072.
9. Paglialonga A et al. (2021) 'eHealth for patients with rare diseases: the eHealth Working Group of the European Reference Network on Rare Multisystemic Vascular Diseases (VASCERN)', *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 16(1), p. 164.
10. Henshall, D.C. et al. (2023) 'Shaping the future of European epilepsy research: Final meeting report from EPICLUSTER', *Epilepsy research*, 189, p. 107068.
11. Smith M et al. (2020) 'Telemedicine strategy of the European Reference Network ITHACA for the diagnosis and management of patients with rare developmental disorders', *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 15(1), p. 103.
12. Del Marmol, V. (2022) 'Prevention and screening of melanoma in Europe: 20 years of the Euromelanoma campaign', *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology : JEADV*, 36 Suppl 6, pp. 5–11.
13. Bernts LHP et al. (2019) 'Position statement on access to care in rare liver diseases: advancements of the European reference network (ERN) RARE-LIVER', *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 14(1), p. 169.
14. Gaupp-Berghausen M et al. (2019) 'Evaluation of Different Recruitment Methods: Longitudinal, Web-Based, Pan-European Physical Activity Through Sustainable Transport Approaches (PASTA) Project', *Journal of medical Internet research*, 21(5), p. e11492.
15. Zwergal A et al. (2016) 'DIZZYNET--a European network initiative for vertigo and balance research: visions and aims', *Journal of neurology*, 263 Suppl 1, pp. S2–S9.

16. de Rojas, T. et al. (2020) 'EORTC SPECTA-AYA: A unique molecular profiling platform for adolescents and young adults with cancer in Europe', *International journal of cancer*, 147(4), pp. 1180–1184.
17. Ruggieri, L. et al. (2020) 'Survey by TEDDY European Network of Excellence for Paediatric Clinical Research demonstrates potential for Europe-wide trials', *Acta paediatrica (Oslo, Norway : 1992)*, 109(3), pp. 607–612.
18. Spanakis, M. et al. (2019) 'PharmActa: Personalized pharmaceutical care eHealth platform for patients and pharmacists', *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 100, p. 103336.
19. Viviani L et al. (2014) 'The European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry: valuable lessons learned on how to sustain a disease registry', *Orphanet journal of rare diseases*, 9, p. 81.
20. Boelens PG et al. (2014) 'Involving patients in a multidisciplinary European consensus process and in the development of a "patient summary of the consensus document for colon and rectal cancer care"', *The patient*, 7(3), pp. 261–270.
21. Rogan E (2014) 'Activities of the European multiple sclerosis platform', *European neurology*, 72 Suppl 1, pp. 43–46.
22. de Rojas, T. et al. (2019) 'Radiotherapy practice for paediatric brain tumours across Europe and quality assurance initiatives: Current situation, international survey and future perspectives', *European journal of cancer (Oxford, England : 1990)*, 114, pp. 36–46.
23. Rodríguez-Gómez, O. et al. (2019) 'The MOPEAD project: Advancing patient engagement for the detection of "hidden" undiagnosed cases of Alzheimer's disease in the community', *Alzheimer's & dementia: the journal of the Alzheimer's Association*, 15(6), pp. 828–839.
24. Selig, W. et al. (2019) 'Incorporating Patient Advocates in Oncology Clinical Development: Lessons Learned From a Novel Pilot Program', *Therapeutic innovation & regulatory science*, 53(3), pp. 349–353.
25. de Lorenzo, F. and Apostolidis, K. (2019) 'The European Cancer Patient Coalition and its central role in connecting stakeholders to advance patient-centric solutions in the mission on cancer', *Molecular oncology*, 13(3), pp. 653–666.
26. Theurich, M.A. et al. (2019) 'Breastfeeding Rates and Programs in Europe: A Survey of 11 National Breastfeeding Committees and Representatives', *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 68(3), pp. 400–407.
27. Ray-Coquard, I. et al. (2019) 'Rare ovarian tumours: Epidemiology, treatment challenges in and outside a network setting', *European journal of surgical oncology : the journal of the European Society of Surgical Oncology and the British Association of Surgical Oncology*, 45(1), pp. 67–74.
28. Imbimbo, M. et al. (2019) 'Mesothelioma and thymic tumors: Treatment challenges in (outside) a network setting', *European journal of surgical oncology : the journal of the European Society of Surgical Oncology and the British Association of Surgical Oncology*, 45(1), pp. 75–80.
29. Zikos D et al. (2009) 'Collection and sharing of information on patient safety education and training in Europe', *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 150, pp. 745–749.
30. Gove, D. et al. (2018) 'Alzheimer Europe's position on involving people with dementia in research through PPI (patient and public involvement)', *Aging & mental health*, 22(6), pp. 723–729.
31. Kluetz, P.G., O'Connor, D.J. and Soltys, K. (2018) 'Incorporating the patient experience into regulatory decision making in the USA, Europe, and Canada', *The Lancet. Oncology*, 19(5), pp. e267–e274.
32. Deybach JC et al. (2006) 'European porphyria initiative (EPI): a platform to develop a common approach to the management of porphyrias and to promote research in the field', *Physiological research*, 55 Suppl 2, pp. S67–S73.
33. Geels, M.J. et al. (2015) 'TRANSVAC research infrastructure - Results and lessons learned from the European network of vaccine research and development', *Vaccine*, 33(41), pp. 5481–5487.

34. Coebergh, J.W. et al. (2015) 'EUROCOURSE recipe for cancer surveillance by visible population-based cancer RegisTrees in Europe: From roots to fruits', *European journal of cancer* (Oxford, England: 1990), 51(9), pp. 1050–1063.
35. Anttila, A. et al. (2015) 'Towards better implementation of cancer screening in Europe through improved monitoring and evaluation and greater engagement of cancer registries', *European journal of cancer* (Oxford, England: 1990), 51(2), pp. 241–251.
36. Monaco, L., Crimi, M. and Wang, C.M. (2014) 'The challenge for a European network of biobanks for rare diseases taken up by RD-Connect', *Pathobiology: journal of immunopathology, molecular and cellular biology*, 81(5–6), pp. 231–236.
37. Burisch, J. et al. (2011) 'Construction and validation of a web-based epidemiological database for inflammatory bowel diseases in Europe An EpiCom study', *Journal of Crohn's & colitis*, 5(4), pp. 342–349.
38. Dolk, H. (2005) 'EUROCAT: 25 years of European surveillance of congenital anomalies', *Archives of disease in childhood. Fetal and neonatal edition*, 90(5), pp. F355–F358.
39. Schmitz, Friederike, et al. "The Potential of E-Health in Patients after Allogeneic Stem Cell Transplantation." *Blood* 140.Supplement 1 (2022): 7966-7967.
40. Al-Batran, S., et al. "P-355 Recruitment of gastrointestinal cancer patients via PLATON Network: An interactive precision oncology platform." *Annals of Oncology* 34 (2023): S139.
41. Hudson, Tom, and Louis J. Denis. "Europa Uomo: the European prostate cancer coalition." *Prostate Cancer* (2007): 267-271.
42. Bøje, Rikke Buus, et al. "What are the barriers towards cervical cancer screening for vulnerable women? A qualitative comparative analysis of stakeholder perspectives in seven European countries." *BMJ open* 14.5 (2024): e079921.
43. Budin-Ljøsne, Isabelle, et al. "Participant engagement and involvement in longitudinal cohort studies: qualitative insights from a selection of pregnancy and birth, twin, and family-based population cohort studies." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 24.1 (2024): 1-13.
44. Marques, Sandra CS, et al. "Improving understanding of participation and attrition phenomena in European cohort studies: protocol for a multi-situated qualitative study." *JMIR research protocols* 9.7 (2020): e14997.
45. Marques, Sandra CS, et al. "Understanding participation in European cohort studies of preterm children: the views of parents, healthcare professionals and researchers." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 21 (2021): 1-14.
46. Lucas, Patricia J., Debra Allnock, and Tricia Jessiman. "How are European birth-cohort studies engaging and consulting with young cohort members?." *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 13 (2013): 1-9.
47. Teixeira, Raquel, et al. "Survey of data collection methods and retention strategies in European birth cohorts of children and adults born very preterm." *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology* 36.5 (2022): 706-714.
48. Aguayo, Gloria A., et al. "Methods to generate innovative research ideas and improve patient and public involvement in modern epidemiological research: review, patient viewpoint, and guidelines for implementation of a digital cohort study." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 23.12 (2021): e25743.
49. Ahrens, Wolfgang, et al. "The IDEFICS cohort: design, characteristics and participation in the baseline survey." *International Journal of Obesity* 35.1 (2011): S3-S15.
50. Dahlin-Ivanoff, Synneve, et al. "Was it worth it? Older adults' experiences of participating in a population-based cohort study—a focus group study." *BMC geriatrics* 19 (2019): 1-12.
51. Nobile, Hélène, et al. "Participants' decision to enroll in cohort studies with biobanks: quantitative insights from two German studies." *Personalized Medicine* 14.6 (2017): 477-485.
52. Mallafré-Larrosa, Meritxell, et al. "Development and Promotion of an mHealth App for Adolescents Based on the European Code Against Cancer: Retrospective Cohort Study." *JMIR cancer* 9.1 (2023): e48040.

53. Ritchie, Craig W., et al. "Development of interventions for the secondary prevention of Alzheimer's dementia: the European Prevention of Alzheimer's Dementia (EPAD) project." *The Lancet Psychiatry* 3.2 (2016): 179-186.
54. Svanes, Cecilie, et al. "Cohort profile: the multigeneration Respiratory Health in Northern Europe, Spain and Australia (RHINESSA) cohort." *BMJ open* 12.6 (2022): e059434.
55. Haas, Matilda A., et al. "'CTRL': an online, Dynamic Consent and participant engagement platform working towards solving the complexities of consent in genomic research." *European Journal of Human Genetics* 29.4 (2021): 687-698.
56. Hoffmann-Vold, Anna-Maria, et al. "Cohort enrichment strategies for progressive interstitial lung disease in systemic sclerosis from European scleroderma trials and research." *Chest* 163.3 (2023): 586-598.

Researcher engagement and incentive strategies for data and sample sharing

57. Bhatti, A. et al. (2024) 'Cohort profile: the European Unified Registries On Heart Care Evaluation and Randomized Trials (EuroHeart)-acute coronary syndrome and percutaneous coronary intervention', *European heart journal. Quality of care & clinical outcomes*, 10(5), pp. 386–390.
58. Collins C (2022) 'The EGPRN Research Strategy for general practice in Europe', *The European journal of general practice*, 28(1), pp. 136–141.
59. Janowczyk A et al. (2022) 'Towards a national strategy for digital pathology in Switzerland', *Virchows Archiv : an international journal of pathology*, 481(4), pp. 647-652.
60. Mañú Pereira, M.D.M. et al. (2023) 'Sickle cell disease landscape and challenges in the EU: the ERN-EuroBloodNet perspective', *The Lancet. Haematology*, 10(8), pp. e687–e694.
61. Chalmers, J.D. et al. (2023) 'Bronchiectasis in Europe: data on disease characteristics from the European Bronchiectasis registry (EMBARC)', *The Lancet. Respiratory medicine*, 11(7), pp. 637–649.
62. Ali SR et al. (2021) 'Supporting international networks through platforms for standardised data collection-the European Registries for Rare Endocrine Conditions (EuRRECa) model', *Endocrine*, 71(3), pp. 555–560.
63. Lim, K.H.J. et al. (2022) 'The impact of COVID-19 on oncology professionals-one year on: lessons learned from the ESMO Resilience Task Force survey series', *ESMO open*, 7(1), p. 100374.
64. Sarno, E. et al. (2021) 'A Review of Significant European Foodborne Outbreaks in the Last Decade', *Journal of food protection*, 84(12), pp. 2059–2070. doi:10.4315/JFP-21-096.
65. Schüngel M and Stackebrandt E (2015) 'Microbial resource research infrastructure (MIRRI): infrastructure to foster academic research and biotechnological innovation', *Biotechnology journal*, 10(1), pp. 17–19.
66. Hämmäläinen, I. et al. (2019) 'Role of Academic Biobanks in Public-Private Partnerships in the European Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure Community', *Biopreservation and biobanking*, 17(1), pp. 46–51.
67. Calvo, F. et al. (2018) 'Cancer Core Europe: A European cancer research alliance realizing a research infrastructure with critical mass and programmatic approach to cure cancer in the 21st century', *European journal of cancer (Oxford, England : 1990)*, 103, pp. 155–159.
68. Milne R et al. (2013) 'EU Pancreas: an integrated European platform for pancreas cancer research--from basic science to clinical and public health interventions for a rare disease', *Public health genomics*, 16(6), pp. 305–312.
69. Bartonova A (2012) 'How can scientists bring research to use: the HENVINET experience', *Environmental health: a global access science source*, 11 Suppl 1, p. S2.
70. Van Royen P et al. (2011) 'Series: The research agenda for general practice/family medicine and primary health care in Europe. Part 6: reaction on commentaries - how to continue with the Research Agenda?', *The European journal of general practice*, 17(1), pp. 58–61.

71. Huttin C and Liebman M (2011) 'Applications of an adaptive knowledge platform in translational medicine for breast cancer', *Technology and health care: official journal of the European Society for Engineering and Medicine*, 19(5), pp. 349–354.
72. Gurinović M et al. (2010) 'Capacity development in food composition database management and nutritional research and education in Central and Eastern European, Middle Eastern and North African countries', *European journal of clinical nutrition*, 64 Suppl 3, pp. S134–S138.
73. Brunfeldt, M. et al. (2018) 'Perceptions of legislation relating to the sharing of genomic biobank results with donors-a survey of BBMRI-ERIC biobanks', *European journal of human genetics : EJHG*, 26(3), pp. 324–329.
74. Psyrris, A. et al. (2010) 'Strategies to promote translational research within the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) Head and Neck Cancer Group: a report from the Translational Research Subcommittee', *Annals of oncology : official journal of the European Society for Medical Oncology*, 21(10), pp. 1952–1960.
75. Simpson, S. et al. (2008) 'Early identification and assessment of new and emerging health technologies: actions, progress, and the future direction of an international collaboration--EuroScan', *International journal of technology assessment in health care*, 24(4), pp. 518–525.
76. Demotes-Mainard, J., Canet, E. and Segard, L. (2006) 'Public-private partnership models in France and in Europe', *Therapie*, 61(4), p. 325.
77. Rajan, Abinaya, et al. "Staff perceptions of change resulting from participation in a European cancer accreditation programme: a snapshot from eight cancer centres." *ecancermedicalscience* 9 (2015).
78. Devriendt, Thijs, Pascal Borry, and Mahsa Shabani. "Credit and recognition for contributions to data-sharing platforms among cohort holders and platform developers in Europe: interview study." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 24.1 (2022): e25983.
79. Larsson, Anthony. "The need for research infrastructures: a narrative review of large-scale research infrastructures in biobanking." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 15.4 (2017): 375-383.
80. Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Data sharing in biomedical sciences: a systematic review of incentives." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 19.3 (2021): 219-227.
81. Simell, Birgit A., et al. "Transnational access to large prospective cohorts in Europe: Current trends and unmet needs." *New biotechnology* 49 (2019): 98-103.
82. Jaddoe, Vincent WV, et al. "The LifeCycle Project-EU Child Cohort Network: a federated analysis infrastructure and harmonized data of more than 250,000 children and parents." *European journal of epidemiology* 35 (2020): 709-724.
83. Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Reward systems for cohort data sharing: An interview study with funding agencies." *Plos one* 18.3 (2023): e0282969.
84. Hardy, Timothy, et al. "The European NAFLD Registry: a real-world longitudinal cohort study of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease." *Contemporary clinical trials* 98 (2020): 106175.
85. Lakerveld, Jeroen, et al. "Towards the integration and development of a cross-European research network and infrastructure: the DEterminants of Diet and Physical ACTivity (DEDIPAC) Knowledge Hub." *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity* 11 (2014): 1-10.

Cohort manager engagement and incentive strategies for data and sample sharing

86. Peyroteo, M. et al. (2024) 'European Health Information Training Programme: a sustainable strategy for strengthening capacity in health information', *European journal of public health*, 34(Supplement_1), pp. i35–i42.

87. Stuurman, A.L. et al. (2023) 'Brand-specific estimates of influenza vaccine effectiveness for the 2021-2022 season in Europe: results from the DRIVE multi-stakeholder study platform', *Frontiers in public health*, 11, p. 1195409.
88. Eva, G. et al. (2022) 'Position paper on management of personal data in environment and health research in Europe', *Environment international*, 165, p. 107334.
89. Wijsenbeek M et al. (2019) 'Design of a Study Assessing Disease Behaviour During the Peri-Diagnostic Period in Patients with Interstitial Lung Disease: The STARLINER Study', *Advances in therapy*, 36(1), pp. 232–243.
90. Stahel, R.A. et al. (2020) 'Current models, challenges and best practices for work conducted between European academic cooperative groups and industry', *ESMO open*, 5(2).
91. van Ommen GJ et al. (2015) 'BBMRI-ERIC as a resource for pharmaceutical and life science industries: the development of biobank-based Expert Centres', *European journal of human genetics : EJHG*, 23(7), pp. 893–900.
92. van Royen P et al. (2010) 'Series: The research agenda for general practice/family medicine and primary health care in Europe. Part 5: Needs and implications for future research and policy', *The European journal of general practice*, 16(4), pp. 244–248.
93. Murray PJ et al. (2009) 'Open source and healthcare in Europe - time to put leading edge ideas into practice', *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 150, pp. 963–967.
94. Klazinga N, Fischer C, Ten Asbroek A. Health services research related to performance indicators and benchmarking in Europe. *J Heal Serv Res Policy*. 2011;16(SUPPL. 2):38–47.
95. Aarden, Erik. "Infrastructuring European scientific integration: Heterogeneous meanings of the European biobanking infrastructure BBMRI–ERIC." *Social Studies of Science* 53.4 (2023): 572-598.
96. Raess, Michael, et al. "Facilitating remote and virtual access provision by European research infrastructures—requirements, issues, and recommendations." *Open Research Europe* 4 (2024): 152.

B.2. List of references from additional, more general literature search

97. Anderson, J. Michael, et al. "Perceptions and Opinions Towards Data-Sharing: A Survey of Addiction Journal Editorial Board Members." *The journal of scientific practice and integrity* 2022 (2022).
98. Shore, Carolyn, et al., eds. "Reflections on sharing clinical trial data: challenges and a way forward: proceedings of a workshop." (2020).
99. Hermansen, Anna, Dean A. Regier, and Samantha Pollard. "Developing data sharing models for health research with real-world data: a scoping review of patient and public preferences." *Journal of Medical Systems* 46.12 (2022): 86.
100. Guerrini, Christi J., et al. "Fresh takes on five health data sharing domains: Quality, privacy, equity, incentives, and sustainability." *Frontiers in big Data* 6 (2023): 1095119.
101. Perrier, Laure, Erik Blondal, and Heather MacDonald. "The views, perspectives, and experiences of academic researchers with data sharing and reuse: A meta-synthesis." *PloS one* 15.2 (2020): e0229182.
102. Klingner, Carsten M., et al. "Research Data Management and Data Sharing for Reproducible Research—Results of a Community Survey of the German National Research Data Infrastructure Initiative Neuroscience." *eneuro* 10.2 (2023).

- 103.Devriendt, Thijs, Pascal Borry, and Mahsa Shabani. "Credit and recognition for contributions to data-sharing platforms among cohort holders and platform developers in Europe: interview study." *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 24.1 (2022): e25983.
- 104.Hood, Amelia SC, and William J. Sutherland. "The data-index: An author-level metric that values impactful data and incentivizes data sharing." *Ecology and Evolution* 11.21 (2021): 14344-14350.
- 105.Woods, H. B., and S. Pinfield. "Incentivising research data sharing: a scoping review." *Wellcome Open Research* 6: 355." 2022,
- 106.Hendriks, Saskia, Khara M. Ramos, and Christine Grady. "Survey of investigators about sharing human research data in the neurosciences." *Neurology* 99.12 (2022): e1314-e1325.
- 107.Devriendt, Thijs, et al. "An agenda-setting paper on data sharing platforms: euCanSHare workshop." *Open Research Europe* 1 (2021).
- 108.Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Policies to regulate data sharing of cohorts via data infrastructures: An interview study with funding agencies." *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 168 (2022): 104900.
- 109.García-Closas, Montserrat, et al. "Moving toward findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable practices in epidemiologic research." *American journal of epidemiology* 192.6 (2023): 995-1005.
- 110.Devriendt, Thijs, Mahsa Shabani, and Pascal Borry. "Data sharing in biomedical sciences: a systematic review of incentives." *Biopreservation and Biobanking* 19.3 (2021): 219-227.
- 111.Rowhani-Farid, Anisa, Adrian Aldcroft, and Adrian G. Barnett. "Did awarding badges increase data sharing in BMJ Open? A randomized controlled trial." *Royal Society open science* 7.3 (2020): 191818.
- 112.Hulsen, Tim. "Sharing is caring—data sharing initiatives in healthcare." *International journal of environmental research and public health* 17.9 (2020): 3046.
- 113.Rowhani-Farid, Anisa, Adrian Aldcroft, and Adrian G. Barnett. "Did awarding badges increase data sharing in BMJ Open? A randomized controlled trial." *Royal Society open science* 7.3 (2020): 191818.
- 114.Scheibner, James, et al. "Revolutionizing medical data sharing using advanced privacy-enhancing technologies: technical, legal, and ethical synthesis." *Journal of medical Internet research* 23.2 (2021): e25120.
- 115.Towse, John N., David A. Ellis, and Andrea S. Towse. "Opening Pandora's Box: Peeking inside Psychology's data sharing practices, and seven recommendations for change." *Behavior Research Methods* 53 (2021): 1455-1468.